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AfDB to support CDA in Climate Adaptation, Scaling of Agricultural Technologies

BAYERO UNIVERSITY
KANO

**CENTRE FOR
DRYLAND AGRICULTURE**
AN AFRICA CENTRE OF EXCELLENCE

CENTRE FOR DRYLAND AGRICULTURE

Bayero University, Kano – Nigeria

... an Africa Centre of Excellence

VISION

Resilient and Prosperous African Drylands

MISSION

To improve livelihood, resilience and sustainable use of natural resources in African drylands through training and demand-driven research

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- Good leadership and Inclusiveness
- Passion and Teamwork
- Commitment and Sacrifice
- Integrity and Transparency
- Professionalism and Excellence

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The AfDB President reading one of the scientific posters of CDA with the VC, Prof. Sagir Abbas and Director CDA, Prof. Jibrin M. Jibrin

AfDB to support CDA in Climate Adaptation, Scaling of Agricultural Technologies

The President of the African Development Bank (AfDB), Dr. Akinwunmi Adesina, has expressed the willingness of the Bank to support the Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) in addressing food security challenges in the drylands of Africa.

Dr. Adesina made this commitment when he visited the CDA on Saturday, 2nd March, 2024 to felicitate with the Centre's MSc and PhD graduates during Bayero University's 38th convocation ceremony.

Dr Adesina said he was impressed with the track record of the CDA, especially in winning multiple grants from the World Bank, MacArthur

Foundation and other donors to address climate adaptation and food security issues in the drylands. He was also particularly impressed with the diversity of students from all over Africa.

"I was very impressed with what the University does in all areas and in particular the rigour they approach their work. I am delighted to be here at this centre, they are doing fantastic work."

"Why this Centre is very important is that we live in an era of climate change and we get only three per cent of agriculture under irrigation, therefore we have to help our farmers to make informed decisions under the uncertainties of climate. Farmers need to have access to

AfDB President, Dr Akinwumi Adesina (right) jotting some notes, during a presentation by Director CDA, while his wife (left) looks on

Director CDA, Professor Jibrin Mohammed Jibrin making a presentation on CDA's historical evolution and achievements to AfDB President, Dr Akinwumi Adesina

technologies that allow their production systems to be resilient in the face of climate change.”

“I am impressed with the work that I saw here. The African Development Bank will support the work they are doing in three to four ways. First, we will work with them to become one of the key centres to get technology such as water-efficient maize, and heat-tolerance wheat varieties to farmers at the scale of millions.

“Secondly we will work with them to also become a centre which we can use in modelling work so that we can know how to predict weather patterns and get that information to farmers so that they can plan better and the Bank will work with them through a program we call Africa Disaster Insurance Facility which supports farmers in countries in the face of climate change.

“The third area that we think is going to be

important is the Agric pitch for people to develop their business ideas and get up to 120,000 dollars in grants. The major thing is to adapt to climate change. We will support CDA to be able to do more and also to be able to have a significant amount of more resources to be able to do more.

“I will make sure that this centre is given priority by the Global Centre on Adaptation which I sit on the board together with the former UN Secretary General, Ban Ki Moon because you are doing exactly what we want to see – supporting farmers in the face of climate change,” he said.

The Director of the Centre, Professor Jibrin Mohammed Jibrin had earlier made a brief presentation about the historical evolution of the Centre, which he said was established in 2012 by the University through a MacArthur Foundation seed grant of \$800,000.

President, AfDB, Dr Akinwumi Adesina, VC, Prof Sagir Abbas, Director CDA, Prof Jibrin M. Jibrin in a group photograph with the entourage of Dr Adesina, PhD and MSc graduates of CDA, CDA team members and Deputy Vice Chancellors of Management Services and Research and Development of BUK

Director of CDA, Prof Jibrin M. Jibrin (left) explaining a point to the Minister of Education, Professor Mamman Tahir (right) at the screen house of CDA Farm, while the VC, Prof Sagir Abbas (3rd left) and other dignitaries listen

FG to Use CDA's Facilities to Train Young Nigerian Entrepreneurs - Minister of Education

The Federal Government is planning to use the state-of-the-art facilities of the Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) to train young entrepreneurs from all parts of the country as part of its initiatives to provide job opportunities and address the increasing rates of unemployment.

The Minister of Education, Professor Tahir Mamman made this assertion on 1st March, 2024, when he visited the CDA's Research and Training Farm, laboratories, and innovation hub. He said the CDA had all it takes to train entrepreneurs at all levels.

The Minister while appreciating the facilities at CDA, said the Federal Government's new policy would be to train young people in basic skills in order to become self-reliant, especially in agriculture, which can absorb millions of them. "The Federal Government will support CDA to provide skills acquisition to the teeming youth, including those that dropped out of

schools," he said.

The Director of CDA, Professor Jibrin Mohammed Jibrin, who took the Minister around the facilities of the Centre along with the Vice Chancellor and other members of the Bayero University management team, informed the Minister that the CDA is a regional centre of excellence funded by the World Bank and French Development Agency (AFD).

He said recently, the Centre is giving greater emphasis to entrepreneurship and innovation. "We are making this centre to provide opportunities to young people to harness their ideas and turn them into viable products and services."

The Director stated that the Centre started "agrihacking" competition last year to provide opportunity for young entrepreneurs to pitch their business ideas for support. In the maiden edition, 90 young entrepreneurs applied out of which 10 were selected to pitch their

agribusiness ideas. He said five were selected for funding and mentoring through a competitive process. The selected 5 are on mentorship to refine their ideas.

According to him, there are some venture capitalists that have shown interest in funding their ideas into products.

The Director noted that the CDA laboratory is a reference hub for fertilizer analysis, “as all fertilizers sold in parts of northern Nigeria have to be analyzed in our laboratories, we do the analysis to see whether they conform with what the companies say and we send the result to the Federal Ministry of Agriculture.

He told the Minister that the CDA Training and Research Farm regularly hosts students from secondary schools to tertiary institutions for either internship, study tour, or attachment.

The Minister then called on Nigerian companies to collaborate with Nigerian universities in order to benefit from the innovations of the universities through research.

We are making this Centre to provide opportunities to young people to harness their ideas and turn them into viable products and services

Vice Chancellor, Professor Sagir Adamu Abbas welcoming the Minister of Education, Professor Mamman Tahir to the CDA Research and Training Farm

The Director CDA, Prof Jibrin M. Jibrin showing the geographical map of the CDA Research and Training Farm to the Minister of Education, Prof. Tahir Mamman

The Minister of Education, Professor Tahir Mamman listening to the functions of CDA laboratory facilities from the Director, Professor Jibrin M. Jibrin

The Vice Chancellor, Professor Sagir Adamu Abbas (standing) commending the CDA for setting pace in research and training in BUK

Review of PG Programmes and Curricula: VC Commends CDA for Setting Pace for Teaching, Research in BUK

The Vice Chancellor, Professor Sagir Adamu Abbas, has commended the Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) for setting the pace for teaching and research at Bayero University, Kano.

The Vice Chancellor was making this commendation at the opening ceremony of the workshop on Curriculum Review of Postgraduate Programmes of the CDA held on Wednesday, 7th February 2024.

The Vice Chancellor stated that the curriculum review was organized in response to the evolving global landscape, compounded by the challenges posed by the recent global pandemic, which have significantly impacted higher education delivery.

"I initiated a committee to review the curricula and mode of delivery of the CDA programmes. This initiative is part of the University's commitment to ensuring improved visibility, wider coverage, and seamless dissemination of knowledge as well as the

sustainability of the Centre and its activities," the Vice Chancellor said.

"With the expertise of committee members drawn from various academic units of the university, including the Deans of the School of Postgraduate Studies and the Faculty of Education Directors of Academic Planning, Centre for Information Technology, Centre for Renewable Energy and Sustainable Transition, Laboratory Management Services, Gender Studies, and the Directorate of Research, Innovation, and Partnership, I am optimistic that this committee has charted a new pathway for the Centre's future and by extension a road map for the wider university community to follow," he added.

According to the Vice Chancellor, it was crucial to reflect on the Centre's journey, particularly its achievements in fulfilling its mission and vision. He noted that significant milestones include the review and validation of the curriculum in January 2018 and the five-

year unreserved international accreditation received from the French High Council for Evaluation of Research and Higher Education (HCERES) in September 2019.

“The university will leverage on the existence of our Centre for Competence in Digital Education (C-CoDE) and other critical infrastructure to support these new programmes, as we navigate to a new mode of delivery,” the VC said.

Earlier in his welcome address, the Director CDA, Professor Jibrin Mohammed Jibrin expressed confidence that with the high caliber of competent personalities involved, significant achievement would be recorded in the review of the curriculum of PG programmes of the Centre.

During the opening session, a keynote address

The university will leverage on the existence of our Centre for Competence in Digital Education (C-CoDE) and other critical infrastructure to support these new programmes, as we navigate to a new mode of delivery

was presented by Professor Christine Iyetunde Ofulue, Director of the Regional Training and Research Institute for Distance and Open Learning (RETRIDOL), National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN), titled “Shaping a Future Ready Education System: Adaptive

Digital Curriculum Design for Transformative Learning.”

At the first plenary session, presentations were made by Professor Sanusi Gaya Mohammed, the Deputy Director, Training of CDA on Overview of the Report of CDA Committee on Gaps Assessment; Experience Sharing on the Implementation of Modular Delivery in Nigerian Universities: Lessons from Africa Centre of Excellence – Centre for Oilfield Chemicals Research (ACE-CEFOR), University of Port-Harcourt by Professor Ogbonna F. Joel; and Effective Digital Curricula for Higher Education by Professor Nebath Tanglang of NOUN, Abuja.

There were syndicate sessions on the review and input into the revised curriculum for each of the CDA programmes.

Group photograph of the participants of workshop on curriculum review of CDA programmes

African Development Bank to Support Young Entrepreneurs Under CDA's AgriHacking Initiative

The African Development Bank (AfDB), has expressed its willingness to support young entrepreneurs under the Centre for Dryland Agriculture's agrihacking initiative.

President of AfDB, Dr Akinwumi Adesina made this pledge on Saturday, 2nd February, 2024, when he visited the CDA and interacted with the management and graduands of the Centre, who have completed their PhD and MSc programmes.

In support of the Centre's initiatives, the AfDB will consider providing a grant for the Centre to bolster the AgriHacking Competition, empowering it to expand its impact further.

The President added that drawing inspiration from the AfDB's Agric-pitch program, CDA would be empowered to organize an annual competition for African innovators with substantial funding, with each winner receiving \$120,000 to realize their ideas.

He commended the Centre's AgriHacking competition for its role in fostering innovative ideas and solutions in agriculture. "Congratulations on your Agric-Hacking for turning agriculture into a business, we should get young people engaged in agribusiness," he remarked.

President, AfDB, Dr Akinwumi Adesina emphasizing on the Bank's commitment to support young entrepreneurs under the CDA's AgriHacking initiative

The Director CDA, Professor Jibrin Mohammed Jibrin, had earlier told the AfDB President that the Centre organised a pitching competition for young entrepreneurs and five of the best business ideas were selected for mentoring and

funding support.

He added that the entrepreneurs were exposed to agribusiness mentorship and knowledge development at the CDA to further broaden their capacity to grow their products and market base.

President, AfDB, Dr Akinwumi Adesina interacting with one of the CDA's PhD students, Susan Ojochide Simon

10th Anniversary of ACE: CDA's Impact Boosts Research Activities in BUK – Vice Chancellor

Intervention from the World Bank under the Africa Centre of Excellence (ACE) project at Bayero University's Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) has impacted positively in the creation of more Research Centres in the University, the Vice Chancellor, Professor Sagir Adamu Abbas, has disclosed.

Speaking on Friday, 22nd March, 2024 while fielding questions on the impact of CDA's ACE project as part of the 10year anniversary of the ACE programme in the institution, Prof. Abbas noted that the Centre had impacted positively in the aspect of increasing research activities in the University.

"Amongst the impacts of CDA

is that it has led to the establishment of many research centres.

In addition, interest in research activities which led to many discoveries has tremendously increased thereby contributing to the creation of ACEPHAP, another beneficiary of ACE project in the University," said the Vice Chancellor.

Professor Abbas noted that the results-based disbursement nature of funding of CDA in particular has made the University management tie reward to performance, which has increased commitment and productivity among the members of staff.

Another impact of the ACE Project was that CDA through

the DLI 7.5 has assisted the university in setting up a Continuing Professional Development (CPD) Unit in the Directorate of Academic Planning as well as strengthening the Guidance and Counseling unit of the University.

The Vice Chancellor disclosed that the University will continue to support CDA.

He said the management had provided funds for teaching and research worth millions of naira as well as in-kind funding which included providing the building housing the center and recently providing well-furnished international students hostels to the CDA.

International postgraduate student hostels given to the CDA by the Management of Bayero University, Kano

CDA Unveils Improved Composite Sorghum Flour Good for Diabetic Patients, Healthy Living

Dr Hakeem Ajiege unveiling the new improved sorghum flour to the participants while Dr Murtala M. Badamasi looks on

The Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) in collaboration with the International Crops Research Institute for the Semi-Arid Tropics (ICRISAT), the University of Reading, and a private company, Tazij, unveiled new sustainable packaging solutions for composite sorghum flours as part of a research recently conducted for healthy living and consumption. The new improved sorghum flour is also

good for diabetic patients and others with health challenges. The sorghum composite flour and the sustainable packaging solutions are outputs from a research funded through the GCRF AgriFood Africa Innovation Awards Round 6.

Briefing journalists on the outcome of research, the Director Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA), Professor Jibrin Mohammed Jibrin said the research was aimed at promoting indigenous food as

it relates to the many impacts on the healthy living of individuals. He added that the nutrient-rich grain would promote food and nutrition security in the country.

According to Professor Jibrin, "Sorghum is rich in vitamins, minerals, dietary fibre and anti-oxidants which help in the management of diabetes, lowering of cholesterol, and boosting energy.

"Sorghum also contains

iron, magnesium, and copper which help in blood circulation to prevent anemia", he added.

The CDA Director said the research, funded by GCRF Agrifood Africa Innovation Awards Round 6 was initiated to address grassroots challenges confronting sorghum cultivation as well as to reduce the importation of the grains.

The lead researcher CDA, Dr Hakeem Ajeigbe, said the advocacy on sorghum production and consumption would increase economic prosperity and address challenges in food processing, distribution, and storage.

Sorghum is rich in vitamins, minerals, dietary fibre and antioxidants which help in the management of diabetes, lowering of cholesterol, and boosting energy. Sorghum also contains iron, magnesium, and copper which help in blood circulation to prevent anemia

He said the research focused on ways to improve the availability and accessibility of safe, healthy, nutritious and sustainable local food.

Earlier, the Head of the Department of Food Science and Technology, BUK, Dr Hauwa Ladi -Yusuf, said composite sorghum flour with soya beans and small cassava targets all age groups, especially diabetic patients.

In the same vein, the Country Director of ICRISAT, Dr Ignatius Angarawai, appealed to the general public to desist from consuming hybrid food, because it could result in cancer.

Staff, postgraduate students and other participants eating the food made up of the new improved sorghum flour

Dr Hakeem Ajiegbe explaining a point to the participants during a practical session

CDA Trains Farmers on Agroecological Best Practices

The Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) has organized a three-day capacity building training for women and youth farmers from across the northern Nigeria on agroecological best practices.

Speaking at the opening ceremony, the Director of the Center, Professor Jibrin Mohammed Jibrin, said the training would help farmers to improve their farming techniques without causing harm to the environment.

He said the training was in collaboration with the Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Food Security.

He added that the training was mainly on how to improve the farming system and maintain the ecosystem.

“Such training is very important considering the fact that this decade, 2021 to 2030, is the United Nation’s Decade of Ecosystem Restoration. We must all agree that in recent years, we have faced a lot of challenges with our ecosystem

and, in particular, in the last few years, areas around Kano, Jigawa, and Bauchi have experienced a huge loss of biodiversity because of many reasons. The charcoal business in recent times is a cause for concern.”

“This training came as a result of a partnership between the Centre for Dryland Agriculture and the National Programme on Food Security towards improving our farming practices and preserving our environment.”

The Director also urged the participants to make use of the knowledge they would acquire during the training.

“I promise you that you are going to have the best type of training on this issue. I welcome you to this training and look forward to interacting with you.”

On his part, the national correspondent of the Agroecology Programme in Nigeria, Yarima Sa'idu, said the primary objective of the training was to support farming families to boost their staple food production capacity on an environmentally sustainable basis.

He stated that it was expected that the knowledge gained by the participants of the training would have a trickle-down effect on production practices across the northwest zone.

He said the Agroecology Programme was aimed at contributing to increasing productivity and agro-sylvo-pastoral and fisheries production through diversified and sustainable production systems, and reducing post-harvest production losses.

This training came as a result of a partnership between the Centre for Dryland Agriculture and the National Programme on Food Security towards improving our farming practices and preserving our environment

Dr Sambo demonstrating compost making to the participants

Practical session on drip irrigation at the CDA Farm

Participants trained on drip irrigation and plastic mulching of tomato in the screen house of CDA Farm

CDA RESEARCH LABORATORY FACILITIES

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CDA TRAINING AND RESEARCH FARM

CDA'S FRESH FROM THE FARM

Fat Content determination:
Utilizing a Soxtec Analyzer
for Precise crude fat
determination

CDA's Cutting-Edge Research

Pinpointing Powerful Traits: PCR Amplification
for Gene Identification in Agriculture

Kjeldahl Distillation: Unveiling the Secrets of Nitrogen
and Protein in plant, food, soil and fertilizer samples

Unlocking the Microbiome: Microscopic
Discovery of fungal spore and bacteria

DNA Profiling: Separating DNA
Fragments with Gel Electrophoresis

Plant Regeneration Revolution:
Formulating Media for Plant Tissue Culture Growth

Grinding Leaves with Liquid
Nitrogen for Nucleic Acid Extraction

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